

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN MITRAL VALVE ANNULUS AND CORONARY DOMINANCE- IMPLICATIONS TO MITRAL VALVE SURGERY

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: The mitral valve, located at the intersection of the left atrium and left ventricle, protects the left atrioventricular orifice and directs unidirectional blood flow during ventricular diastole. If the mitral valve is irreparably damaged, it should be replaced with a valve made of biological tissue, metal, pyrolytic carbon, vulcanized silicon rubber, or similar materials. Prostheses for synthetic valves require extensive knowledge of mitral orifice and valve size. The current study examined the size of the mitral aperture and valve in adult human heart specimens from autopsy. **Materials and Methods:** This study examined 100 adult human hearts from autopsy. The left atrium was opened along the heart's left border, exposing the mitral orifice. The diameter of the valve was then measured using a digital vernier calliper and the circumference was determined manually. **Results:** The mean annular circumference of the mitral valve were 106.525 ± 9.82 mm, maximum in males 112.921 ± 0.850 mm. Annular circumference is maximum in Left dominant hearts 108.494 ± 9.466 . **Conclusion:** our study has large mitral valve annulus measurements compared to other research and left dominant hearts shows maximum annulus measurements. Comparison between annulus circumference and dominance pattern is a novelty study done in this study. This work could assist cardiothoracic surgeons and prosthetic valve manufacturers in estimating mitral valve size and also to assess the annular circumference based on dominance pattern.

Keywords: Valve circumference, Prosthetic valve, Valve diameter, Mitral valve, Coronary dominance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The heart is an essential organ of the circulatory system. Valves ensure that blood flows unidirectionally. The mitral valve (MV) prevents blood from flowing back into the left atrium. All valves must be intact for the heart to operate properly. The structure includes an aperture, annulus, cusp, supporting chordae tendineae, and papillary muscles^{1,2}. The cardiac skeleton is made up of four bands of connective tissue that separate the atria and ventricles, including the fibrous mitral annulus, which anchors the valves and influences their forces³. The mitral annulus is a flexible structure that anchors the mitral valve attachments and changes shape over the cardiac cycle. The form is oval, with a longer intercommissural length than anterior-posterior length⁴. Although the annular structure varies significantly between patients, its functioning remains consistent⁵. The mitral annulus is a ring that connects the anterior and posterior leaflets. The anterior (aortic) leaflet is larger than the posterior (mural) leaflet and covers one-third of the annulus⁴. It is classified into three regions: A1, A2, and A3⁴. The anterior leaflet of the mitral valve is in fibrous continuity with the aortic valve, while the posterior annulus is mostly muscular⁴. The posterior leaflet has longer attachments, covering around two-thirds of the annulus, but is significantly thinner than the anterior leaflet². The posterior leaflet has distinct areas (P1, P2, and P3) separated by tiny indentations around its free edge. The size of the P2 segment varies based on the overall annulus size⁴. The annulus has two locations where the leaflets connect: the anterior commissure and posterior commissure. The anterior commissure is between A1 and P1, while the posterior commissure is between A3 and P3. Coaptation between the two leaflets reduces mechanical stress during ventricular systole^{2, 6}. The chordae tendinae anchor the anterior and posterior leaflets of the mitral valve to papillary muscles in the left ventricle³. Before ventricular systole, the papillary muscles contract, pulling the tendinous cords taut. Maintaining this tension during contraction protects the mitral valve leaflets from being pushed into the left atrium by LV pressure. These components form the architecture that maintains mitral valve function and unidirectional blood flow between the left heart chambers. Mitral valve pathology requires surgery to rectify due to physiological degradation of any structures within the system.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Requirements

For the purpose of this study, 100 fresh cadaveric human hearts were procured from Forensic department of Rajarajeshwari medical college and hospital. Instruments used in the study are Digital Vernier callipers, Dissection forceps (pointed, toothed, blunt), Scalpel, Scissors, String to outline the annulus.

2.2 Ethical consideration:

Ethical clearance is taken in 2019 from IEC of Rajarajeshwari medical college and hospital Bengaluru (RRMCH-IEC/175/2019-20) on 23/12/2019.

2.3 Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

Inclusion criteria: age group from 20 years to 60 years.

Exclusion criteria: above 60 years and below 20 years.

2.4 Study design:

The study population Age ranging between 20-60 years consisting of 57 (57%) males and 43(43%) females. The following methodology was performed on all hearts within this study. The dominant pattern of the coronary arteries was analysed. A left atriotomy was performed in which a longitudinal incision was made down the midline of the posterior atrial wall, between the pulmonary veins, abutting at the level of the mitral annulus. Subsequent perpendicular incisions at the inferior aspect of the longitudinal incisions created two flaps that exposed the mitral valve leaflets and annulus. After a left atriotomy, three measurements were taken to assess the mitral valve annulus: anterior-posterior length, inter-commissural length, and circumference. The anterior-posterior length was measured from the A2 leaflet midline to the P2 leaflet midline, whereas the inter-commissural length was measured from the anterior to the posterior commissure. The annulus circumference was determined by outlining it with a string and measuring the resulting length.

2.5 Statistical analysis:

Statistical analysis of the data was achieved using chi-square test to compare gender and dominance pattern. T-test conducted to compare gender and mitral valve annulus measurements. one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni 't' test conducted to Compare mitral valve annulus measurements with dominance pattern. A probability of 0.05 and less was considered as statistically significant. SigmaPlot 14.5 version (Systat Software Inc., San Jose, USA) was used for statistical analysis and for plotting of graphs.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Pattern of coronary dominance:

72 heart specimens presented with right dominance pattern (38 male + 34 female), 17 with left dominance pattern (11 male+6 female) and 11(8 male + 3 female) with codominance pattern. (Table 1, Figure 1)

S.No.	Variable	Category	Male	Female	Statistics
1	Dominance pattern	Right	38	34	$\chi^2 = 2.046$ P = 0.360
		Left	11	6	
		Codominant	8	3	

n = 100
The ' χ^2 ' and 'P' values are by chi-square test.

3.2 Mitral Valve Annulus Characterization

3.2.1 Comparison of mitral valve measurements for gender

Males showed higher average values for all mitral valve measurements than females, particularly in terms of annulus circumference (Table 3.2.1). In a study of 100 hearts, the average anterior-posterior length was 17.588 ± 0.562 mm in males and 16.106 ± 0.540 mm in females, inter-commissural length was 40.054 ± 2.024 mm in males and 35.315 ± 1.144 mm in females, and annulus circumference was 112.921 ± 6.416 mm in males and 100.281 ± 4.472 mm in females. (Table 2, Graph 1)

S. No.	Parameter	Gender	Mean	SE	Statistics
1	Antero-posterior Length (mm)	Male	17.588	0.0744	t = 13.280 P < 0.001
		Female	16.106	0.0823	
2	Inter-commissural Length (mm)	Male	40.054	0.268	t = 13.774 P < 0.001
		Female	35.315	0.174	
3	Annulus Circumference (mm)	Male	112.921	0.850	t = 11.046 P < 0.001
		Female	100.281	0.682	

n – Male = 57; Female = 43; Total = 100.
The 't' and 'P' values are by Student's 't' test.

3.2.2 Comparison of mitral valve measurements for dominance pattern (DP)

Co dominant (CD) hearts shows maximum APL & ICL measurements (17.457 \pm 0.745&38.669 \pm 2.373 respectively), whereas AC is maximum in Left dominant (LD hearts) (108.494 \pm 9.466). Right dominant (RD) hearts show minimum measurements in APL ICL & AC (16.812 \pm 0.910 37.766 \pm 2.853 & 107.191 \pm 8.387 respectively). (Table 3)

S.No.	Parameter	DP	Mean	SE	Statistics
1	Antero-posterior Length – APL (mm)	RD	16.812	0.107	F = 3.305 P = 0.041
		LD	17.209	0.227	
		CD	17.457	0.225	
2	Inter-commissural Length- ICL (mm)	RD	37.766	0.336	F = 0.949 P = 0.691
		LD	38.651	0.823	
		CD	38.669	0.716	
3	Annulus Circumference - AC (mm)	RD	107.191	0.988	F = 0.173 P = 0.842
		LD	108.494	2.296	
		CD	107.855	2.350	

n – Right dominant (RD) = 72; Left dominant (LD) = 17; Co-dominant (CD) = 11; Total = 100.
 The ‘F’ and ‘P’ values are by one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni ‘t’ test.

4. DISCUSSION

The mitral annulus is an important part of the heart's central fibrous skeleton. Accurate anatomical information is critical for minimizing complications during MV intervention. The mitral valve annulus was characterized, and the results were consistent with previous literature. The fibrous annulus differs between people and can have a short anterior-posterior dimension⁵. Males had higher MV measurements than females, which is a common gender difference in anatomical investigations.

The prevalence of coronary dominance in the population remains a source of controversy. Reports vary from 58% right dominant, 10% left dominant, and 32% codominant⁷, to 81.17% right dominant, 2.35% left dominant, and 16.47% codominant⁸. In our study, 72 heart specimens presented with right dominance pattern (38 male + 34 female), 17 with left dominance pattern (11 male + 6 female), and 11 (eight male + three female) with codominance pattern.

The Department of Anatomy at Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College in Belgaum measured the mitral valve size in fifty adult cadaveric hearts from North Karnataka using a cardiac sizer. The mean annular circumference and diameter of the valve was 8.03 ± 0.82 cm. In his investigation, the majority (72%) of the mitral valves measured between 7.53 and 8.47 cm in size⁹. These values are lower than those found in our study. The difference between our study and theirs could be attributed to different methods and materials.

A study conducted in Maharashtra using the dissection approach revealed that the average circumference of the mitral valve is 9.34 cm. The investigation involved 30 cadaveric hearts. These values are lower than those found in our study¹⁰. Rajathi et al studied sixty adult cadaveric hearts in Chennai, India and found that the average mitral valve circumference is 8.86 ± 0.16 cm. This value is lower than those found in our mean values¹¹.

Shakthivel et al. discovered an average annulus circumference of 8.29 cm in South India¹². In normal Caucasian individuals, mitral circumference ranges from 7-11cm. However, dilated cardiomyopathy can cause it to reach 8-18cm¹³. Parmatma P Mishra et al. studied 120 adult cadaveric hearts and found that 55.83% of the mitral valves had a circumference between 7.5 and 10 cm. Arithmetic mean was 8.7 cm with a SD of 1.68¹⁴.

Amgain, *et al* studied 50 cadaveric adult human hearts *and* mean annular circumference of the mitral valve was found to be 8.03 ± 0.82 cm¹⁵. Gupta, C et al studied 18 adult cadaveric isolated hearts. Mean circumference of the mitral valve was found to be 9.11 ± 0.44 cm¹⁶. Shruthi B. N et.al studied 60 formalin fixed human cadaveric hearts. Mean circumference of the mitral valve was found to be $7.98\text{cm} \pm 1.83\text{cm}$ ¹⁷. Oliveira D et al did review study on Geometric description for

the anatomy of the mitral valve and Mean circumference of the mitral valve was found to be 106 ± 10^{18} .

Our study found significant relationships between MV circumference and dominance pattern. In this study, the mean annular circumference of the mitral valve was 106.525 ± 9.82 mm, maximum in males 112.921 ± 0.850 mm. Annular circumference is maximum in Left dominant hearts 108.494 ± 9.466 .

Table 4: Comparison of mitral valve annulus size between previous study and present study

Sr. No	Name of author	Year	Circumference (cm)	Method of study
1	Rusted, I. E <i>et al.</i>	1952	9.9	Dissection method
2	Brock RC	1952	10.05	Dissection method
3	Chiechi <i>et al</i>	1956	10.00	Dissection method
4	Louis A and Du Plessis	1964	10.10	Dissection method
5	Bulkley and Roberts	1975	9.00	Dissection method
6	Ormiston JA	1981	9.30	2D echocardiography
7	Tetsuro Sakai	1990	9.33	Dissection method
8	Sakai T	1999	9.33	Dissection method
9	Andrade et al	2005	7.92	Dissection method
10	Patil et al	2009	8.248	Dissection method
11	Gunnal, et al	2012	9.12	Dissection method
12	Amgain, et al	2013	8.03±0.82	Cardiac sizer after dissecting
13	Gupta C, et al	2019	9.11±0.44	Dissection method
14	Shruthi B. N, et al	2019	7.98±1.83	Dissection method
15	Oliveira D, et al	2020	10.6±1.00	Dissection method
16	Current.study	2024	10.652±0.98	Dissection method

5. CONCLUSION

There have been very few studies on morphometric assessments of mitral valve annulus in cadaveric hearts. The majority of the investigations include two-dimensional or three-dimensional echocardiography, with measurements taken during the cardiac cycle. Nonetheless, given the scarcity of investigations on cadaveric hearts, the current study's findings are compared to those of imaging techniques. Our study also found significant relationships between MV circumference and dominance pattern and it's a novelty study because no other studies found to assess relationships between MV circumference and dominance pattern.

Conflict of interest: None to be declared by all the authors.

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